

COVINFORM

CORONAVIRUS VULNERABILITIES AND INFORMATION DYNAMICS RESEARCH AND MODELLING

D9.4 Podcasts

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Executive Summary

This deliverable describes our approach for developing the COVINFORM podcasts, as one of the project's tools to disseminate and communicate the project results to our target audiences. Due to the nature of the medium, general public and scientific community have been identified as the target audience for the podcast. Podcasts have been chosen as a means of one-way communication with the target audiences, given their potentially broad demographic reach and the gaining popularity of this format. In addition to the benefits of the podcasts, the nature of the medium enables the COVINFORM project to communicate key messages without having to radically simplify their meaning.

The title of the podcast series (*Beyond Numbers – COVID-19 pandemic & Society*) has been chosen to reflect COVINFORM's key messages. The framework of intersectionality will be the main theme in most of the episodes, connecting various subjects the COVINFORM project encounters in its research. It is intended that each episode will look at each of the identified subjects and further provide a more detailed explanation of terminology, application of the theory in the COVID-19 pandemic and the impact on vulnerable groups.

The podcasts will target a mixed audience, which has been chosen based on the already established COVINFORM audience, the format of the medium and the podcast context. The mixed target audience consists of the general public and the scientific community. The first episode of the podcast will be launched at the end of January 2022, and the other episodes will then be published every following month, for a total of five podcasts.

The episode topics have been carefully curated to reflect and amplify COVINFORM's areas of research. Overall, the scope of the themes will not only comprehensively communicate COVINFORM's aims, but will also establish a thorough and accessible resource of information regarding the COVID-19 pandemic and its impact on society. The list of episodes can be seen below. Once the episodes become public, they will be accessible via podcast's public RSS feed - <https://rss.com/podcasts/beyondnumbers/>.

- Episode 1 - Intersectionality & Vulnerability
- Episode 2 - Communication & Public Health Campaigns
- Episode 3- Data, Memes & Misinformation
- Episode 4 - Gender & Inequalities
- Episode 5 - Government & Recommendations

The podcast series is a task led by Trilateral Research as Work Package 9 (WP9) leader and podcast coordinator and is carried out in collaboration with all project partners.

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1 Introduction

The COVINFORM podcast is a demonstrator deliverable, which follows the deliverable *D9.2 Communication plan*. Podcast has been chosen as a means of one-way communication with the target audiences, given their potentially broad demographic reach and the gaining popularity of this format. In addition to the benefits of the podcast, the nature of the medium enables the COVINFORM project to communicate key messages without having to radically simplify their meaning.

Firstly, this report outlines the concept of the podcast, which has been formed together in a collaborative way among consortium members to reflect and amplify the main messages of the COVINFORM project, alongside other communication and dissemination activities (e.g. videos, bi-monthly reports, social media engagement etc.). To ensure the right target audiences are reached, this report establishes, based on the *D9.2 Communications plan*, the selected target audiences for this particular means of communication. The report also acknowledges an appropriate timeframe in which the podcast will be produced, recorded and published, using the first episode as an example of episode planning. Furthermore, the process of choosing episode topics is also discussed, as this has also been a collective process. Lastly, the report encloses a detailed description of each episode, the rationale for each topic and the names of guest speakers, so far confirmed.

2 Podcast strategy

2.1 Concept

The concept of the podcasts has been discussed on multiple occasions with the project coordinator as well as with the consortium, who agreed that the key message of the podcast should amplify the main takeaways of the COVINFORM project. Thus, the podcast will focus on the impact of COVID-19 on various intersecting vulnerabilities and the role of communication and governmental response to the COVID-19 pandemic.

The title of the podcast series (*Beyond Numbers – COVID-19 pandemic & Society*) has been chosen to reflect the above-mentioned concept and key messages. The framework of intersectionality will be the main theme in most of the episodes connecting various subjects the COVINFORM project encounters in its research. It is intended that each episode will look at each of the identified subjects and further provide a more detailed explanation of terminology, application of the theory in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic and the impact on vulnerable groups. The chosen topics and the rationale behind their selection is discussed more broadly in section 2.4 *Episode Topics* of this deliverable.

2.2 Target Audiences

As far as the target audiences for the podcast are concerned, the consortium have agreed to cater to a mixed audience. On one hand, podcasts as a communication medium are gaining popularity amongst the general public, thus this specific target audience is one of the essential groups targeted. In *D9.2 Communications plan*, COVINFORM has established key messages relevant to different target audiences. In the case of the general public, the main message the COVINFORM project wants to convey is the understanding of various measures such as lockdowns, social isolation, mental and physical health etc. and their impact on society as a whole.

However, the COVINFORM podcast aims to communicate the main message from an intersectional point of view. Hence the second essential target audience is identified as the scientific community and academia. The COVINFORM project appeals to this particular target audience by contributing towards knowledge production within the fields of social sciences. Since the podcast will also discuss theoretical frameworks, which will be explained and applied to different topics, the scientific community and academia are a direct target audience that could benefit from such material. Moreover, the podcast will communicate scientific insights and theoretical frameworks in an accessible and easy-to-understand way. Thus, it will be possible to raise the interest in the general population while still providing relevant scientific input to the scientific community. In addition, both chosen target audiences may be interested in receiving information on COVINFORM's analysis of current responses and communication strategies employed by national planners and healthcare decision-makers.

2.3 Timeline

In order to keep the audience engaged, the podcast will come out on a periodic basis. The aim is to publish one episode per month, starting with the first episode published in January 2022. Consequently, the second episode will be published at the end of February, the third episode will be published at the end of March and so forth, for a total of five podcasts.

The regularly scheduled publishing date will not only help our audience to navigate the publishing schedule and manage their expectations relating to the podcasts' frequency, but it will also aid the consortium when it comes to episode planning. To assure an attainable level of planning, each episode will be planned almost two months ahead of the publishing date. To date, episode two, which is planned for the end of February, has already been planned and the speakers confirmed.

Table 1. Example of episode planning & timeline showcased for Episode 2

Date	Task
10-21.1.2022	Meeting with COVINFORM guest speakers to go over the timeline & key messages
22.1.2022	Speakers confirmed
24.1.2022	Script first draft sent to the speakers & project coordinator
24.1.-2.2.2022	Revision period for the script
4.2.2022	Script finalised
7-11.2.2022	Episode 2 rehearsal
14-18.2.2022	Episode 2 recording
28.2.2022	Episode 2 release date

2.4 Episode topics

The COVINFORM podcast series is estimated to consist of five episodes covering various topics and themes encountered during the project. From a planning point of view, it has been decided to include two major themes within one episode. Nevertheless, it is essential that the two subjects are related and complement each other – either theoretically or practically. The topics have been identified from other material produced within the COVINFORM project, such as blogs, bi-monthly reports and whitepapers. In addition, the topics have been assessed during a Work Package (WP) 9 calls organised by Trilateral Research in November 2021. The partners had a chance to cooperate and brainstorm identified topics and suggest new ones. The collaborative process helped identify the most relevant topics, which have been selected and paired together.

Table 2 shows an overview of the planned episodes with the topic as well as the expected release date. Each episode topic description will be outlined in section 2.5 *Executive plan* of this deliverable.

Table 2. Podcast episode topics overview

Episode	Topic	Date published
Episode 1	Intersectionality & Vulnerability	30.1.2022
Episode 2	Communication & Public Health Campaigns	28.2.2022
Episode 3	Data, Memes & Misinformation	31.3.2022
Episode 4	Gender & Inequalities	30.4.2022
Episode 5	Government & Recommendations	31.5.2022

2.5 Executive plan

2.5.1 Episode 1 – Intersectionality & Vulnerability

The topic of the first episode has been chosen based on the importance of the two concepts for future episodes. It is fundamental that the frameworks of intersectionality and vulnerability are discussed and explained so the listener can grasp the implied message of the whole podcast series. The first episode also sets the scene and introduces the COVINFORM project, as it is going to be a frequent point of reference.

The episode starts with an introduction to the COVINFORM project, as mentioned above and it also introduces the speakers, Dr Viktoria Adler from SYNIO and Jil Molenaar from the University of Antwerp. The debate then moves to the background of intersectionality and vulnerability, touching upon Black feminism, the historical evolution of the theory on vulnerability and providing a general overview of the two concepts. The episode further offers exploration on how these two concepts come together in COVINFORM and complement each other.

In addition, the episode includes various examples of intersecting vulnerabilities. On the one hand, the aim is to focus on relatable and easily understandable examples from real-life situations, so the general public can better imagine and apply the theoretical concepts. On the other hand, the theory-focused content will be of benefit to the scientific community, as it promotes knowledge production in the field of social science drafted from the preliminary results of COVINFORM research and analysis.

2.5.2 Episode 2 - Communication & Public Health Campaigns

The second episode will focus on the topics of communication with a special segment on the public health campaigns. Communication is a concept tightly related to intersectionality and vulnerability; topics discussed in the first episode. The second episode will follow the discussion from episode one and enrich the concept of communication with the application to pandemic management.

According to the plan (see Table 1), the podcast guests are already confirmed at the time of submission of this deliverable. Partners participating in the production of the second episode are Dr Su Anson from Trilateral Research and Marva Arabatzi from KEMEA. The second episode will also include an external guest, Panagiotis Alefragis, who is the digital head of The Newtons Laboratory responsible for the production of public health campaigns in Greece.

As part of the episode, the COVINFORM experts will also introduce the concept of behaviour change and discuss elements of inclusive communication during a crisis, which is a part of COVINFORM WP7's focus. Furthermore, the preliminary results from COVINFORM research will be shared in the form of lessons learned. At the end of this episode, examples of public health campaigns will be communicated alongside Panagiotis' experience from producing such campaigns.

2.5.3 Episode 3 – Data, Memes & Misinformation

Episode three will concentrate on no less important topic, which is data. On the one hand, during the pandemic, the general public has faced an unprecedented encounter with a great amount of data such as the infection rates, but also more complicated statistical data for example from vaccine trials. On the other hand, the COVINFORM project is built on an interesting and innovative research methodology, which will be also a point of interest for the third episode. A partner from Trilateral Research, Niamh Aspell, will be responsible for explaining the methodology and research design in an accessible way, so the listeners (both the scientific community and the general public) can learn more

about the COVINFORM project as well as how the data is leveraged in social science research. On top of that, topics such as memes and misinformation relating to COVID-19 will be touched upon, to establish examples of how important data science is.

2.5.4 Episode 4 - Gender & Inequalities

The first episode has established a list of inequalities that have been either uncovered or deepened during the COVID-19 pandemic. The fourth episode will thus pay close attention to those inequalities and discuss them in more depth. The first and foremost inequality that will serve as an example of unequal systems will be gender. The debate will include many examples to establish the different impacts based on the chosen inequalities. Nevertheless, following the intersectional approach of the project, gender is not going to be the only addressed inequality. The guests will also discuss other inequalities such as disability, age, socioeconomic status or sexuality.

2.5.5 Episode 5 – Government & Recommendations

The fifth and last episode of the COVINFORM podcast will be about governments, public health, communities and recommendations. Governments are considered the main coordinators of the response to the COVID-19 pandemic. They play an essential role when it comes to the effective management of the balance between the public health commitment and legal and ethical frameworks. The episode will discuss the findings of the research that the COVINFORM project conducted regarding governmental structures, social, economic, cultural, and legal factors that influenced specific governmental responses, communication measures and specific adaptations each country took towards specific vulnerable groups.

3 Conclusions

The report has established that the COVINFORM podcast – *Beyond Numbers: COVID-19 pandemic & Society* – will be a communication medium with a potentially large demographic reach. The intersectionality will be the critical lens through which the podcast will examine, deconstruct and communicate themes analysed and researched in the COVINFORM project.

The podcast will target a mixed audience, which has been chosen based on *D9.2 Communication plan*, the format of the medium and the podcast context. The mixed target audience consists of the general public and the scientific community. The first episode of the podcast will be released at the end of January 2022. The other episodes will be then published every following month.

The collaborative process aided in choosing the episode topics, which have been carefully curated to reflect and amplify COVINFORM's areas of research. The episodes include topics such as Intersectionality, Communication, Data, Inequalities and Government response. Overall, the scope of the themes will not only comprehensively communicate COVINFORM's aims, but will also establish a thorough and accessible resource of information regarding the COVID-19 pandemic and society.

4 Podcast availability

The podcast will be available on multiple streaming platforms (Spotify, Apple Podcast, Google Podcast) as well as on the COVINFORM website. Please find the link to podcast's RSS feed below.

Episode 1: <https://rss.com/podcasts/beyondnumbers/>

Also available on [Spotify](#) and [Apple Podcasts](#).